

MODERN METHODS OF FACIAL REJUVENATION: SYNERGY OF MINIMALLY INVASIVE AND SURGICAL TECHNIQUES**Mirazim Zaidov***Swiss Montreux Business School***Abstract**

Modern aesthetic facial surgery is aimed at achieving a natural, harmonious result with minimal trauma and a shortened rehabilitation period. The article discusses current trends and techniques in the field of facial rejuvenation, including minimally invasive technologies, SMAS-lifting, lipofilling, as well as the use of regenerative medicine and energy-based devices. Clinical algorithms for choosing the optimal treatment strategy are shown, taking into account the anatomical and age characteristics of the patient. Real clinical cases and an overview of the latest international studies are presented.

Keywords: facial surgery, SMAS-lifting, lipofilling, regenerative technologies, energy-based devices, rejuvenation, endoscopy, PRP, aesthetic medicine

Introduction

In recent decades, aesthetic medicine has evolved from standard surgical interventions to a comprehensive and personalized approach. Modern patients expect not only an improved appearance, but also minimal trauma, rapid recovery and a long-lasting effect. This dictates the need to integrate surgical and non-surgical methods within a single rejuvenation program.

Modern aesthetic facial surgery strives to combine innovative technologies with an individualized approach aimed at achieving a natural and harmonious result with minimal trauma and a shorter rehabilitation period. Every year, more and more methods appear that allow not only to effectively rejuvenate, but also to restore the natural anatomy of the face. In recent decades, much attention has been paid to minimally invasive techniques such as endoscopic lifting, SMAS lifting, lipofilling, as well as the use of energy-based devices and regenerative medicine. These techniques help solve problems of age-related changes in the middle and lower third of the face, improve contours, restore lost volume, and stimulate natural tissue regeneration processes. Age-related changes in the face are complex and affect both deep and superficial structures.

Modern aesthetic facial surgery in medicine

Loss of soft tissue volume, including in the middle third of the face, gravitational tissue drooping (ptosis), loss of skin elasticity, and bone structure deformations (for example, in the orbital and upper jaw areas) require a precise approach and comprehensive correction. Modern aesthetic surgery is aimed at eliminating these changes by acting on both the skin and deeper tissue layers. One of the most popular methods is SMAS lifting, which is aimed at correcting deep tissues, such as the superficial musculoaponeurotic system (SMAS). This method allows for a long-term effect (up to 10 years) with a significant improvement in the facial contour. The SMAS lifting technique involves tissue tightening, which results in significant rejuvenation. However, in recent years, endoscopic facelift has been increasingly used, which is a less invasive method with minimal incisions, which significantly reduces the recovery period. Endoscopic intervention is often combined with blepharoplasty, which allows for comprehensive rejuvenation.

Minimally invasive procedures such as lipofilling, which uses the patient's autologous fat enriched with stem cells, serve as a supplement to surgical methods [6, p.2681]. This allows not only to restore lost volume in the face, but also to improve the quality of the skin. Autologous fat can replace fillers because it has many of the properties of fillers, including biocompatibility, easy availability, low cost, abundant, and can be harvested easily and frequently, with minimal complications [3, p.62]. Lipofilling can be used as an independent technique or in combination with other operations to achieve a more natural and long-lasting result. In parallel with this, the use of PRP therapy (platelet-rich plasma) is developing, which stimulates tissue regeneration, accelerates the healing of postoperative areas and improves skin texture. One of the new trends is the use of energy-based technologies such as high-intensity ultrasound (HIFU), radiofrequency (RF) lifting and laser therapy. These methods act on the deep layers of the skin, stimulating the synthesis of collagen and elastin, which helps tighten and improve the texture of the skin. The use of these technologies in combination with traditional surgical interventions significantly increases the effectiveness of the procedures, reduces the rehabilitation period and minimizes the risks associated with surgical interventions.

Digitalization in aesthetic surgery plays an important role, allowing for precise planning of interventions using 3D visualization. This not only increases the accuracy of the procedures, but also allows patients to better understand the expected results, which increases their level of satisfaction. 3D modeling helps the surgeon accurately predict changes in the face and minimize the risk of complications. The use of such technologies in aesthetic surgery changes the approach to treatment, making it more personalized and predictable.

Integrating surgical and non-surgical methods in one treatment plan can significantly increase the effectiveness of rejuvenation procedures. This is especially important when it comes to middle-aged and older patients, in whom age-related changes affect several anatomical zones at once. In such cases, a combination of SMAS lifting with lipofilling, laser resurfacing and regenerative methods such as PRP allows not only to rejuvenate the face, but also to preserve its natural contours and facial expressions. In addition, it is important

to note that perioperative patient management, including postoperative procedures such as lymphatic drainage massage, the use of biostimulators and the use of recovery devices, significantly reduces the rehabilitation time and improves the results. Recent studies have shown that proper postoperative therapy and an individual approach to each patient can not only improve the appearance, but also reduce the risk of complications.

Modern aesthetic surgery is not only a technique, but also an art based on a deep understanding of the anatomy, physiology of aging and the individual needs of each patient. It is important to strive to ensure that interventions remain as safe as possible, and their results are natural and harmonious. It is expected that in the future, regenerative medicine and molecular correction of aging will occupy an increasingly important place in the practice of aesthetic surgeons. It should be especially noted that facelift remains the cornerstone of facial and neck rejuvenation [1].

Facial aging is not only a loss of volume and the appearance of wrinkles, but also changes in the microstructure of the skin, deterioration of its texture, and a decrease in turgor. Facial aging is primarily caused by loss of collagen and elastin, displacement of glycosaminoglycans, increase in fat deposits in various locations, changes in muscle relaxation and length, and changes in bone shape [2, p.1108]. All this must be taken into account when planning rejuvenation procedures. For example, the skin loses its elasticity and begins to "sag", especially in the cheek area, around the eyes, and on the neck. To correct such changes, not only surgical methods are used, but also techniques aimed at restoring tissue at the cellular level. In recent years, the use of stem cells has become an important part of anti-aging therapy, which makes it possible to effectively restore skin structures and stimulate tissue regeneration. Therapy using stem cells, in particular, from adipose tissue (adipocytes) or mesenchymal stem cells, is actively used in practice to restore volume and improve the quality of the skin. An additional innovation is the use of biologically active implants, such as collagen fibers, which are introduced into the deep layers of the skin. These implants stimulate the production of the body's own collagen, which can significantly improve the elasticity and structure of the skin. Unlike traditional fillers, such materials not only help restore volume, but also contribute to a long-term effect by strengthening the collagen framework. With the development of technology, it has become possible to use new generation laser systems, such as fractional lasers, which allow treating both superficial and deeper layers of the skin. Fractional lasers, for example, stimulate skin cell renewal by creating microdamage in the skin, which leads to the activation of the process of its restoration and renewal. This technique is actively used to treat wrinkles, post-acne, pigmentation and other skin defects. Facial aging is a dynamic and multifactorial process. Various factors, such as environmental factors and internal factors of the body, cause facial skin aging [4, p.1327].

Regenerative technologies continue to develop, and the possibility of using cell therapy using growth

factors to restore facial tissue is currently being actively studied. Particular attention should be paid to therapy using exosomes - small bubbles that are secreted by cells and have the ability to regenerate and restore tissue. Research in this area promises a revolution in rejuvenation, since exosomes can help stimulate cell division and restore skin structures without surgery. Many of the invasive techniques used today, such as soft tissue fillers, and non-invasive treatments, such as laser therapy and radiofrequency or ultrasound-based skin tightening techniques, have been introduced in the last decade [5, p.8].

Against the background of these technologies, hybrid techniques are becoming increasingly popular, which combine classical surgical approaches with advanced innovations. For example, SMAS lifting and laser resurfacing are often combined, which allows not only to tighten tissues, but also to improve skin texture, reduce scarring and make the result more natural. Such combined procedures allow to achieve optimal results, while minimizing risks and recovery time.

Cosmetic surgery actively uses new approaches in the field of telemedicine, which allows doctors to evaluate the results of the postoperative condition and provide remote consultations. In recent years, the use of mobile applications and platforms for monitoring the patient's condition after surgery has increased. This not only improves the quality of postoperative care, but also helps to reduce the rehabilitation time.

Particular attention should be paid to approaches that are focused on preserving the patient's individuality. For example, recently more and more attention has been paid to the concept of "natural rejuvenation", when surgical interventions are aimed at maintaining the natural expression of the face, rather than radically changing it. It is important that the face remains recognizable, and age-related changes are not perceived as artificial or distorted.

These approaches require a high level of skill from specialists and a deep understanding of the anatomical, physiological and cultural characteristics of each patient. Consultation and procedure planning should include not only technical aspects, but also attention to the psycho-emotional state of the patient, his expectations and needs. Innovations in surgery and aesthetic medicine are not limited to new methods. It is important that with the development of technology, increasingly accurate and safe diagnostic methods are emerging. For example, the use of 3D scanning allows us to obtain a detailed picture of the patient's facial structure, as well as predict how certain interventions can affect their appearance. This is especially important when working with patients who have pronounced age-related changes or anomalies in the anatomy of the face. In addition, age-related changes can be significantly slowed down if preventive methods are used at the first stages of aging. This includes the active use of injection techniques - such as botulinum therapy and dermal fillers, which prevent the formation of wrinkles and maintain youthful skin without the need for serious surgical interventions. Such methods are becoming popular among younger patients interested in maintaining attractiveness throughout their lives.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be noted that modern aesthetic surgery is not just rejuvenation, but the creation of harmony between the internal state of a person and his appearance. In the future, we can expect an even greater expansion of opportunities for personalized rejuvenation, where each patient will have the opportunity to choose an individual program suitable for his skin type, physiological characteristics and life circumstances.

The combination of surgical and non-surgical methods opens up new horizons in facial rejuvenation. This approach allows for individualization of treatment, reduction of risks and achievement of the most natural result. In the future, the main focus will be on regenerative medicine, molecular correction of aging and biointegrative technologies.

References

1. Ahmed M Hashem, Rafael A Couto, Eliana F R Duraes, Çagri Çakmakoğlu, Marco Swanson, Chris Surek, James E Zins (2020). Facelift Part I: History, Anatomy, and Clinical Assessment, *Aesthetic Surgery Journal*, Volume 40, Issue 1, Pages 1–18, <https://doi.org/10.1093/asj/sjy326>
2. Arthur Swift, Steven Liew, Susan Weinkle, Julie K Garcia, Michael B Silberberg (2021). The Facial Aging Process From the “Inside Out”, *Aesthetic Surgery Journal*, Volume 41, Issue 10, Pages 1107–1119, <https://doi.org/10.1093/asj/sjaa339>
3. Diepenbrock R.M, Green J.M. (2018). Autologous fat transfer for maxil-lofacial reconstruction. *Atlas Oral Maxillofac Surg Clin North Am.*;26 (1):59-68.
4. Imadojemu S, Sarwer DB, Percec I. (2013). Influence of surgi-cal and minimally invasive facial cosmetic procedures on psy-chosocial outcomes: a systematic review. *JAMA Dermatol.*2013;149(11):1325-1333.
5. Liu, Yin; Mao, Rui MS†; Xiao, Minqin; Zhu, Weidong; Liu, Yang; Xiao, Hong (2024). Facial Rejuvenation: A Global Trend of Dermatological Procedures in the Last Decade. *Plastic & Reconstructive Surgery-Global Open* 12(6): p e5801. | DOI: 10.1097/GOX.0000000000005801.
6. Lotfi E, Ahrami-yanpour N, Khosravi S. (2024). New autologous fat implantation technique for face lifting: A pilot study. *J Cosmet Dermatol*; 23: 2681-2685. doi:10.1111/jocd.16318